

Outcome of Percutaneous Balloon Mitral Valvotomy in Patient with Rheumatic Mitral Stenosis: A Single Centre ExperienceNirav Kumar¹, Ravi Vishnu Prasad², Akanksha Sinha³, Chandrabhanu Chandan⁴, Gautam Kumar⁵¹Additional Professor, Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India²Additional Professor and HOD, Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India³Resident (DM Trainee), Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to evaluate MR severity and its changes after BMV in patient with rheumatic mitral stenosis.**Material & Methods:** We prospectively evaluated consecutive patients with severe rheumatic MS undergoing BMV using the Inoue balloon technique (between) in between the duration of 2 years, functional class and echocardiographic and catheterization data, including MVA, mitral valve mean and peak gradient (MVPG and MVMG), left atrial (LA) pressure, pulmonary artery systolic pressure (PAPs), and MR severity before and after BMV, were evaluated.**Results:** Complete pre-and post-BMV evaluation was performed in 150 patients (100 females) at a mean age of 45.80 ± 14.36 (range = 20 to 76) years. There were 96% females and 79% females in increased MR severity and MR severity without change respectively. The patients with an increased MR degree after BMV had a significantly higher calcification score and a lower MVA before BMV. The patients with an increased MR degree after BMV had a significantly higher calcification score and a lower MVA before BMV. MR increased in tandem with an increase in the calcification score. Most cases with increased MR post BMV had commissural MR in the anterior commissure and were more likely to have commissural rupture. After BMV, MVA significantly increased, whereas PAPs, LA pressure, MVPG and MVMG were significantly reduced.**Conclusion:** In our study, BMV had excellent immediate hemodynamic and clinical results inasmuch as MR severity increased only in some patients and, interestingly, decreased in a few. Our results, underscore BMV efficacy in severe MS. The echocardiographic calcification score was useful for identifying patients likely to have MR development or MR increase after BMV.**Keywords:** Balloon valvuloplasty, Mitral valve insufficiency, Echocardiography.

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Introduction

Rheumatic heart disease is a widely prevalent problem in developing countries, accounting for 25-40% of all cardiac disease. [1] Rheumatic mitral stenosis is common and may occur in young patients. [2] Mitral stenosis is more often caused by rheumatic heart disease. Other causes of mitral stenosis include severe calcification of the mitral annulus and congenital defects of the mitral valve. [3,4,5] Until the early 1980s, surgery was the only possible treatment for severe mitral stenosis; then, a new alternative appeared, percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty (PMV). Since its introduction in 1982 by Inoue et al. [6], PMV has been used successfully as an alternative to open or closed surgical mitral commissurotomy for the treatment

of patients with symptomatic rheumatic mitral stenosis [7]

First described in 1984 by Inoue, percutaneous balloon mitral valvotomy (PMV) has now become a recognized and common therapeutic approach [8] and is used as an alternative to surgical mitral commissurotomy in patients with symptomatic severe mitral stenosis (MS) and suitable valve anatomy. [9] BMV produces significant changes in mitral valve morphology and improvement in leaflet mobility. [10] With an increase in the use of BMV, the effectiveness of this procedure has become widely accepted despite its risks. [11,12] BMV has considerably high success rates and low

complication rates in short-term and long-term followups. [13] This complication is usually mild and well tolerated but MR degree may increase in 25%-83% of cases after BMV. [14]

Hence the aim of the study was to evaluate BMV outcome with an emphasis on MR changes.

Material & Methods

A prospective study including 150 consecutive patients with rheumatic severe MS who were eligible for BMV using the Inoue balloon technique in between the duration of 2 years were included. The study was approved by the institutional Review Board, and all the patients gave their informed consent for the procedure.

Inclusion criteria

Symptomatic severe MS with New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional class (FC) II or more, mitral valve area (MVA) $\leq 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$, and mitral valve echocardiographic score ≤ 11 , according to the scoring system described by Wilkins et al. [15,16]

The presence of each of the following factors was considered an exclusion criterion: left atrial (LA) thrombus; MR severity higher than moderate; unfavorable mitral valve morphology; and need for cardiac surgery because of severe aortic, tricuspid, or coronary disease. The results of our previous study [17] showed that a high echocardiographic score is not a contraindication for BMV in rheumatic MS. The patients who met the exclusion criteria were referred for surgical treatment. The decision regarding BMV was mainly based on echocardiographic assessment, which was employed to measure MVA, valvular and subvalvular apparatus calcifications, and MR degree. The Wilkins score was used to determine the anatomic characteristics of the valve and subvalvular regions. [16] All the patients underwent BMV using the transvenous trans-septal antegrade technique from the right femoral vein. [8] The initial balloon size was chosen according to the patient's height. The balloon size was chosen to obtain an effective balloon dilation area/ body surface area of approximately $4 \text{ cm}^2 / \text{m}^2$. The balloon size was stepwise increased by 0.5 mm consecutive dilations until an MVA $> 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ was reached or MR significantly increased.

Right and left heart pressures, including simultaneous LA and left ventricular (LV) end diastolic pressure (trans-mitral gradient), were measured before and after BMV. The BMV procedure was terminated once the gradient was $\leq 4 \text{ mmHg}$, there was no diastolic rumble, or in case MR occurred or increased.

Standard transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) was performed almost one week before and 24

hours after BMV with a GE Vivid 7 scanner, equipped with an M3S multi-frequency phased array transducer and tissue Doppler imaging facility. Data were acquired with the subjects at rest, lying in the lateral supine position. Grey-scale images were obtained using second-harmonic imaging (1.7/3.4 MHz). Two-dimensional (2D) electrocardiography (ECG) was superimposed on the images, and end-diastole was considered at the peak R-wave of the ECG. Left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was determined using the Simpson biplane method by measuring the end-diastolic and end systolic volumes in 2D images. All the measurements, including MVA, mitral valve peak gradient (MVPG), mitral valve mean gradient (MVMG), MR severity, LA pressure, and pulmonary artery systolic pressure (PAPs), were obtained in accordance with the American Society of Echocardiography (ASE) recommendations.

Transesophageal echocardiography (TEE) was performed on the same day or on the day before intervention for the exclusion of LA thrombi, better evaluation of mitral valve structure, Wilkins score, and MR severity (grades 1-4), interatrial septal thickening measurement, and reassessment of TTE data. [18-20] The MV score was judged according to the Wilkins score system, obtained by adding the score of each of these individual morphological features: leaflet mobility; thickness; calcification; and subvalvular thickening. [15] A score of 0-4 was assigned to each component in accordance with the Wilkins echocardiographic scoring system. Adding the individual scores generally resulted in a total echocardiographic score, which varied from 0 to 16 for the MV, with higher values representing increased morphological abnormality.¹⁵ In this study, the final total echocardiographic scores ranged from 5 to 12.

After BMV, color Doppler echocardiography was used to screen left-to-right atrial shunts. LV gram was performed in all the patients before and after BMV to assess MR severity.

Statistical Analysis

The data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The variables were compared before and after the procedure using the paired samples t-test (continuous variables) or the chi-squared test (categorical variables). The continuous variables were compared between the patients with and without an increase in MR severity and between the patients with and without a decrease in MR severity using the independent samples t-test. A p value was considered significant when it was ≤ 0.05 . Data were collected and analyzed using SPSS statistical package version 16.0 (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

Table 1: Comparison of baseline and echocardiographic characteristics in patients with and without increased MR after BMV

	Increased Severity (n=50)	MR without Change (n=100)	P value
Age (y)	45.55±12.48	45.25±14.56	0.093
Gender (female)	48 (96)	78 (78)	0.118
Ejection fraction (%)	54.46±3.87	51.69±4.66	0.136
Mean Wilkins echocardiographic score	8.00±0.92	8.52±1.38	0.064
Favorable valve anatomy (Wilkins Score ≤ 8)	16 (32)	48 (48)	0.188
Unfavorable valve anatomy (Wilkins Score > 8)	34 (68)	54 (54)	0.314
Wilkins score components			
Mobility	2.14±0.49	2.06±0.44	0.564
Calcification	2.02±0.52	1.52±0.48	< 0.001
Thickness	2.07±0.43	2.08±0.52	0.885
Subvalvular	2.29±0.42	2.48±0.56	0.220
Mitral valve area (cm ²)	0.82±0.25	0.91±0.19	0.017
Pulmonary artery peak systolic pressure (mmHg)	45.00±8.82	48.02±10.20	0.224
Left atrial pressure (mmHg)	26.44±4.86	26.24±4.36	0.729
MV peak gradient (mmHg)	21.49±4.26	21.29±4.86	0.824
MV mean gradient (mmHg)	12.48±3.57	12.58±3.77	0.822

Complete pre-and post-BMV evaluation was performed in 150 patients (100 females) at a mean age of 45.80 ± 14.36 (range = 20 to 76) years. There were 96% females and 79% females in increased MR severity and MR severity without change respectively. The patients with an increased MR degree after BMV had a significantly higher calcification score and a lower MVA before BMV.

Table 2: Hemodynamic and echocardiographic characteristics before and after BMV

	Before BMV	After BMV	P value
Mitral valve area (cm ²)	0.68±0.22	1.86±0.24	< 0.001
Pulmonary artery peak systolic pressure (mmHg)	45.05±10.12	36.84±6.34	< 0.001
Left atrial pressure (mmHg)	25.15±4.56	17.33±4.16	< 0.001
Mitral valve peak gradient (mmHg)	20.16±4.86	9.71±2.76	< 0.001
Mitral valve mean gradient (mmHg)	11.49±3.87	5.85±2.48	< 0.001
MR severity			0.913
No MR	102 (68)	96 (64)	
MR 1+	30 (20)	24 (16)	
MR 2+	18 (12)	28 (18.66)	
MR 3+	0	2 (1.33)	

MR increased in tandem with an increase in the calcification score. Most cases with increased MR post BMV had commissural MR in the anterior commissure and were more likely to have commissural rupture. After BMV, MVA significantly increased, whereas PAPs, LA pressure, MVPG and MVMG were significantly reduced.

Discussion

Rheumatic heart disease complicates pregnancy in a high number of women in countries like India with high endemicity of rheumatic fever. Mitral

stenosis remains the commonest valvular heart disease encountered during pregnancy in India. [21] Mitral stenosis is poorly tolerated in pregnancy because of increased hemodynamic burden. There is a physiological increase in heart rate, blood volume during pregnancy which cannot be accommodated in the heart with mitral stenosis. This leads to increase in mean left atrial pressure, and pulmonary venous pressure which may precipitate heart failure and pulmonary edema especially during the third trimester and peripartum period. [22,23] The risk of maternal death is greatest during labor and the immediate postpartum

period. There is auto transfusion from the uterus during this time, which reaches the central circulation. This suddenly increases the pre-load immediately after delivery, leading to decompensation. This auto transfusion continues upto 24-72 h after delivery and thus the chance of decompensation continues until that time. A significant number of patients remain symptomatic in-spite of optimum medical therapy, necessitating mechanical relief of mitral stenosis. The immediate hemodynamic effectiveness of balloon mitral valvuloplasty in the relief of rheumatic mitral stenosis is apparent from various studies as well as the present. However, long-term results are still being evaluated. Closed mitral valvotomy with its low risk, low cost, large experience, time-tested effectiveness, and large number of cases of mitral stenosis requiring surgery, remains the favored procedure for the relief of critical mitral stenosis in India. Balloon mitral valvuloplasty, however, presents a viable alternative in patients who are unwilling to undergo surgery for personal or cosmetic reasons or in patients in whom surgery is contraindicated due to coexistent medical illness. If facilities exist, there is no doubt that open mitral valvotomy is the best form of repair for a mitral valve multilated by the rheumatic process. [24-27]

Complete pre-and post-BMV evaluation was performed in 150 patients (100 females) at a mean age of 45.80 ± 14.36 (range = 20 to 76) years. There were 96% females and 79% females in increased MR severity and MR severity without change respectively. The patients with an increased MR degree after BMV had a significantly higher calcification score and a lower MVA before BMV. The patients with an increased MR degree after BMV had a significantly higher calcification score and a lower MVA before BMV. MR increased in tandem with an increase in the calcification score. Most cases with increased MR post BMV had commissural MR in the anterior commissure and were more likely to have commissural rupture. After BMV, MVA significantly increased, whereas PAPs, LA pressure, MVPG and MVMG were significantly reduced. It has been previously demonstrated that an $MVA \geq 2 \text{ cm}^2$ can be achieved irrespective of the technique used in most patients. [28,29] In our study, there was a significant improvement in hemodynamic variables, including MVA, PAPs, LA pressure, MVPG, and MVMG after BMV. The increase in MVA was $\leq 2 \text{ cm}^2$ in most of the patients. It is believed that a higher increase in MVA can be achieved only at the expense of more frequent complications. [30] However, in our study, a higher than twofold increase in MVA with no complications shows the efficacy of BMV.

Most studies have evaluated the effect of hemodynamic and echocardiographic variables on

the BMV outcome. Aslanabadi and colleagues [31] evaluated repeated BMV and mitral valve replacement in patients (even with a Wilkins score > 11) who had restenosis after primary balloon valvotomy and achieved acceptable results. Similarly, other studies have shown that a high Wilkins mitral score is not a very robust predictor of poor outcomes after BMV. [32,33] In our study, BMV was successful in all the patients. We evaluated the factors that could influence MR severity or MR development. A higher calcification score and a lower MVA before BMV predicted a rise in MR, but the total Wilkins score could not predict its occurrence. In contrast, Abascal and colleagues [34] reported that an increase in MR could not be predicted by any features of the valve or the subvalvular apparatus, clinical characteristics of the patient, or technical aspects of the procedure. Also worthy of note is that Pan et al [35] found no predictors for the development of significant MR after BMV.

Conclusion

In our study, BMV conferred excellent immediate hemodynamic and clinical results inasmuch as MR severity increased only in some patients and, interestingly, decreased in a few. What is more, there were no major complications. Our results, therefore, give emphasis to the efficacy of BMV in the treatment of patients with severe MS. The echocardiographic calcification score was useful for identifying patients likely to have MR development or MR increase following BMV.

References

1. Community control of rheumatic heart disease in developing countries. I. A major health problem. WHO Chron 34, 336 (1980)
2. Roy S, Bhatia M, Lazaro E, Ramalingaswami V. Juvenile mitral stenosis in India. The Lancet. 1963 Dec 7;282(7319):1193-6.
3. Palacios IF. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty—state of the art. Mini-invasive Surg. 2020;4(73):2574-1225.
4. Palacios IF, Arzamendi D. Percutaneous Mitral Balloon Valvuloplasty for Patients with Rheumatic Mitral Stenosis. Interventional Cardiology Clinics. 2012 Jan 1;1(1):45-61.
5. Palacios IF. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty: worldwide trends. J Am Heart Assoc 2019;8:e012898.
6. Inoue K, Owaki T, Nakamura T, Kitamura F, Miyamoto N. Clinical application of transvenous mitral commissurotomy by a new balloon catheter. The Journal of thoracic and cardiovascular surgery. 1984 Mar 1;87(3):394-402.
7. Palacios IF. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty. Percutaneous Interventions for

- Congenital Heart Disease. London: Informa Healthcare. 2007 Mar 20;177e184.
8. Inoue K, Owaki T, Nakamura T, Kitamura F, Miyamoto N. Clinical application of transvenous mitral commissurotomy by a new balloon catheter. *J Thorac Cardiovasc Surg* 1984;87:394-402.
 9. Fawzy ME. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvotomy. *Catheter Cardiovasc Interv* 2007; 69:313-321.
 10. Hasan-Ali H, Shams-Eddin H, Abd-Elseyed AA, Maghraby MH. Echocardiographic assessment of mitral valve morphology after percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy (PTMC). *Cardiovascular Ultrasound*. 2007 Dec; 5:1-8.
 11. Iung B, Cormier B, Ducimetiere P, Porte JM, Nallet O, Michel PL, Acar J, Vahanian A. Immediate results of percutaneous mitral commissurotomy: a predictive model on a series of 1514 patients. *Circulation*. 1996 Nov 1;94(9):2124-30.
 12. Palacios IF, Block PC, Wilkins GT, Weyman AE. Follow-up of patients undergoing percutaneous mitral balloon valvotomy. Analysis of factors determining restenosis. *Circulation*. 1989 Mar;79(3):573-9.
 13. Dighero H, Zepeda F, Sepúlveda P, Soto JR, Aranda W. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvotomy: six-year follow-up. *J Invasive Cardiol* 2001; 13:795-799.
 14. Arora R, Kalra GS, Singh S, Mukhopadhyay S, Kumar A, Mohan JC, Nigam M. Percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy: Immediate and long-term follow-up results. *Catheterization and cardiovascular interventions*. 2002 Apr;55(4):450-6.
 15. Sadeghian H, Salarifar M, Rezvanfard M, Nematipour E, LOTFI TM, SAFIR MA, POORHOSEINI HR, Semnani V. Percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy: significance of echocardiographic assessment in prediction of immediate result.
 16. Wilkins GT, Weyman AE, Abascal VM, Block PC, Palacios IF. Percutaneous balloon dilatation of the mitral valve: an analysis of echocardiographic variables related to outcome and the mechanism of dilatation. *Heart*. 1988 Oct 1;60(4):299-308.
 17. Aslanabadi N, Jamshidi P, Gaffari S, Ayatollahi Z, Kazemi B, Javadzadegan H. Clinical symptoms of mitral stenosis therapy in men and women. *Journal of Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences*. 2007 Mar 20;10(4).
 18. Baumgartner H, Hung J, Bermejo J, Chambers JB, Evangelista A, Griffin BP, Iung B, Otto CM, Pellikka PA, Quiñones M. Echocardiographic assessment of valve stenosis: EAE/ASE recommendations for clinical practice. *European Journal of Echocardiography*. 2009 Jan 1;10(1):1-25.
 19. Jang IK, Block PC, Newell JB, Tuzcu EM, Palacios IF. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvotomy for recurrent mitral stenosis after surgical commissurotomy. *The American journal of cardiology*. 1995 Mar 15;75(8):601-5.
 20. Armstrong WF, Ryan T. Mitral valve disease. In: Armstrong WF, Ryan T, eds. *Feigenbaum's Echocardiography*. 7th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2010. p. 297-310.
 21. Vijaykumar M, Narula J, Reddy KS, Kaplan EL. Incidence of rheumatic fever and prevalence of rheumatic heart disease in India. *International journal of cardiology*. 1994 Mar 1;43(3):221-8.
 22. Metcalfe J, Ueland K. Maternal cardiovascular adjustments to pregnancy. *Progress in cardiovascular diseases*. 1974 Jan 1;16(4):363-74.
 23. Elkayam U, Bitar F. Valvular heart disease and pregnancy: part I: native valves. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*. 2005 Jul 19;46(2):223-30.
 24. Inoue K, Owaki T, Nakamura T, Kitamura F, Miyamoto N. Clinical application of transvenous mitral commissurotomy by a new balloon catheter. *The Journal of thoracic and cardiovascular surgery*. 1984 Mar 1;87(3):394-402.
 25. Lock JE, Khalilullah M, Shrivastava S, Bahl V, Keane JF. Percutaneous catheter commissurotomy in rheumatic mitral stenosis. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 1985 Dec 12;313(24):1515-8.
 26. Al Zaibag M, Al Kasab S, Ribeiro P, Al Fagih M. Percutaneous double-balloon mitral valvotomy for rheumatic mitral-valve stenosis. *The Lancet*. 1986 Apr 5;327(8484):757-61.
 27. Palacios I, Block PC, Brandt SE, Blanco PA, Casal H, Pulido JJ, Munoz S, D'empaire G, Ortega MA, Jacobs M. Percutaneous balloon valvotomy for patients with severe mitral stenosis. *Circulation*. 1987 Apr;75(4):778-84.
 28. Salarifar M, Rezvanfard M, Sadeghian H, Safir-Mardanloo A, Shafii N. Mitral annular calcification predicts immediate results of percutaneous transvenous mitral commissurotomy. *Cardiovascular ultrasound*. 2011 Oct; 9:1-8.
 29. Waller BF, Vantassel JW, McKay C. Anatomic basis for and morphologic results from catheter balloon valvuloplasty of stenotic mitral valves. *Clinical cardiology*. 1990 Sep;13(9):655-61.
 30. Hildick-Smith DJ, Taylor GJ, Shapiro LM. Inoue balloon mitral valvuloplasty: long-term

- clinical and echocardiographic follow-up of a predominantly unfavourable population. *European heart journal*. 2000 Oct 1;21(20):1690-7.
31. Aslanabadi N, Golmohammadi A, Sohrabi B, Kazemi B. Repeat percutaneous balloon mitral valvotomy vs mitral valve replacement in patients with restenosis after previous balloon mitral valvotomy and unfavorable valve characteristics. *Clinical cardiology*. 2011 Jun; 34(6):401-6.
 32. Feldman T, Carroll JD, Isner JM, Chisholm RJ, Holmes DR, Massumi A, Pichard AD, Herrmann HC, Stertzer SH, O'Neill WW. Effect of valve deformity on results and mitral regurgitation after Inoue balloon commissurotomy. *Circulation*. 1992 Jan;85(1): 180-7.
 33. Uddin MJ, Rahman F, Salman M, Hussain KS, Rahman MS, Hossain MA, Anam K, Rahman MM, Ahmed MK. Percutaneous mitral balloon valvuloplasty in patients with previous surgical mitral commissurotomy. *University Heart Journal*. 2009 Aug 18;5(1):9-12.
 34. Abascal VM, Wilkins GT, Choong CY, Block PC, Palacios IF, Weyman AE. Mitral regurgitation after percutaneous balloon mitral valvuloplasty in adults: evaluation by pulsed Doppler echocardiography. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*. 1988 Feb 1;11(2):257-63.
 35. Ju-Pin P, Shoa-Lin L, Jorge UG, Tsui-Leih H, Chung-Yin C, Shih-Pu W, Chiang BN, Mau-Song C. Frequency and severity of mitral regurgitation one year after balloon mitral valvuloplasty. *The American journal of cardiology*. 1991 Feb 1;67(4):264-8.